

In the cases of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and $\text{CCl}_4 - n - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$ binaries, the alkyl chains are comparatively longer and the alcohol molecules are comparatively less strongly hydrogen bonded than in the case of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ binary. The association matrix, though strong enough to accommodate the CCl_4 molecules in alcohol rich mixtures, becomes less efficient in alcohol poor mixtures and ultimately breaks down due to dielectric effects of CCl_4 which then acts as diluent. Thus, in alcohol rich mixtures, the order is enhanced giving +ve η^E with CCl_4 molecules in the centre surrounded by alcohol molecules. While in the alcohol poor mixtures, the order is decreased giving -ve η^E with alcohol molecules in the centre surrounded by CCl_4 molecules. This explains the occurrence of a +ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ with $(X_A)_{max} < 0.5$ in the alcohol rich mixtures together with a -ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ with $(X_A)_{max} > 0.5$ in alcohol poor mixtures for each of the two cases considered. On the other hand in the case of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{iso-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$ binary, the alkyl chain is longer and branched. Moreover, the alcohol concerned is still less hydrogen bonded than in the cases discussed earlier. Consequently, the association matrix is weak and unable to accommodate the CCl_4 molecules which in effect act as diluent throughout the composition range of the binary. As such η^E values are always negative with -ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ at $(X_A)_{max} < 0.5$. This explanation is further substantiated by the behaviour of the systems 12 to 16 in Table 1.

Thus from the data of Table 1, the applicability of the conditions specified earlier is amply justified for the binary mixtures of polar-polar, polar-apolar and apolar-apolar components provided none of them is strongly associated; while the mixtures of small apolar molecules with lower alcohols having strong hydrogen bonding, deviate from the expected behaviour. However, the anomalous behaviour is explained on the consideration of the tendency of such apolar molecules to get accommodated in the association matrix of the corresponding alcohol in the binary.

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Excess Volumes of Mixing of Some Electron Donating Hydrocarbons with an Electron Accepting Liquid Chlorobenzene

D. K. AGARWAL and (Miss) SUSHMA AGARWAL

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow, U. P. India

Manuscript received 11 January 1978 ; accepted 3 March 1978

IN continuation of our earlier studies on excess volumes of some polar and nonpolar liquids with N-methylacetamide (NMA)¹, Propylene carbonate (PC)², Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)³ and N,N'-Dimethylformamide (DMF)⁴, we have now extended the work on the binary mixtures of some electron donating hydrocarbons with highly electron accepting liquid chlorobenzene. We report excess volumes of chlorobenzene + cyclohexane, + benzene, + toluene, + xylene, and + mesitylene at 30°. In the present work the series of five hydrocarbons was selected because it was thought that electron donating power of hydrocarbons would increase down the series. Excess volumes of these hydrocarbons with hexafluorobenzene have been reported earlier⁵.

Experimental

Cyclohexane, xylene and mesitylene of A. R. grade were twice distilled and the middle fraction was collected. The procedure for purifying the other liquids and for measuring the excess volumes has been described elsewhere¹. The results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It may be noted from Table 1 that excess volume of mixing V_m^E for all the five systems is negative over the entire concentration range. The negative values of V_m^E shows a stronger interaction between the components of the mixture. From the plots, the excess volume of mixing at equimolar concentration were calculated and these values are recorded in Table 2.

It is clear from Table 2 that V_m^E at a constant mole fraction decreases as the electron donating power of hydrocarbons increases. This shows that greater the difference in electronegativity of the components, greater is the interaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. S. S. Tewari, Head of Chemistry Department for valuable suggestions and providing all laboratory facilities. One of us (S.A.) is obliged to the C.S.I.R., India, for the financial help.

